

Supplementary material for the manuscript entitled 'Food marketing on the International Food and Beverage Alliance's Mexican websites during COVID-19' by Nieto C, et al.

Supplementary Annex 1. Manual to explore Mexican Websites committed to the International Food and Beverage Alliance.

HOW-TO MANUAL TO EXPLORE WEBSITES' FOOD AND BEVERAGE MARKETING

- Each coder reviewed the websites of the main companies he/she was assigned to and identified each one's product websites.
- For example: Danette's website is hosted by the Danone group
<http://grupodanone.com.mx/marcas/danone/danette.aspx>
- But it also has its own product webpage: <http://www.danette.com.mx/>
- The individual page will be placed in the variable next to the Website list, on Website 2.

Consecutive number	Brand	Product	Website 1	Website 2
1	DANONE	DANUP	http://grupodanone.com.mx/marcas/danone/danup.aspx	
2	DANONE	DANETTE	http://grupodanone.com.mx/marcas/danone/danette.aspx	http://www.danette.com.mx/
3	DANONE	DANONINO	http://grupodanone.com.mx/marcas/danone/danonino.aspx	http://www.danonino.com.mx/
4	DANONE	ACTIVIA	http://grupodanone.com.mx/marcas/danone/activia.aspx	https://www.activia.com.mx/
5	DANONE	BENEGASTRO	http://grupodanone.com.mx/marcas/danone/benegastro.aspx	http://www.benegastro.com.mx/

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

*We included all products commercialized by IFBA food and beverage companies. For example, if Levité from Bonafont has a page for each flavor of Levité, the page of each flavor will be added into different rows with its respective website.

*Only pages with a Mexican domain (.mx).

* Only official pages. For example, supermarket's webpages were excluded.

*Only pages in Spanish.

*Products that were not eatable on their own, e.g., powders, condiments, and sauces.

*Milk formulas, food supplements, and products that are not food and beverages will be excluded.

PROCEDURE

- Each coder visits the main page (example: kellogss.com.mx).
- From the main page, coders coded all the variables and analyzed the whole page by clicking on all subsections with unlimited clicks.
- On the product pages (for example: chocokrispies.com.mx), the limit will be 5 clicks.
- Each click takes you to a secondary page. On secondary pages, the clicks are stopped.
- The main/home page and their respective secondary pages would be coded and analyzed.
- Videos embedded in the general page do not count as clicks.
- Only videos from the general page are clicked and evaluated, for example if the video shows teenagers in a bar, it can be counted for the variable targeted advertising.
- Social responsibility, child protection, and use of cookies do not count as a click.
- Variables "sponsorships/partnerships", "social/philanthropic responsibility" and "child protection" will be observed after "End time" at the end of the recording.